

MANAGEMENT ETHICS OF SCHOOL LEADERS

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Abstract: In school education, the formation of a team of leaders with management culture and high professional etiquette is the most relevant factor in the process of managing the school team. Therefore, the thoughts on the formation of management principles in education management in future personnel are expressed in this article.

Key words: school, leadership, assessment, style, management, education, morality, situation.

Managing a school is a creative process and a unique art. This pedagogical process is reflected in the different work methods of school leaders. These methods allow each leader to learn theoretically and practically the current issues of school science, to study advanced pedagogical experiences in the field of school education, and the opinion of influential people in this field (employees of public education bodies, school teachers and educators) on school management. and requires the study of opinions and the creative use of these opinions and opinions in the process of managing school work. This, in turn, is of great importance in managing school work and further improving the leadership style.

When the head of each school makes a decision on this or that issue of educational work, when he organizes its implementation, when he supervises the work of his subordinates (teachers, class leaders, tutors, etc.), he acts in accordance with his duties. said. But each leader works in this in his own way, with different effective methods that determine the management process, which is unique to him. It should be emphasized that no two people are exactly the same, and no two leadership styles are exactly the same. The style of leadership is formed in the direct communication of leaders with their subordinates, in their mutual relations. The style of leadership is characterized by beliefs such as democracy, community, high responsibility and political consciousness, initiative.

The style is formed by the totality of social relations in the team, but the style mainly depends on the leader. The same leader realizes the close interdependence of the school's educational and economic work. Success in his work is determined by many factors.

Every leader is an educator. He should fully have a sense of high responsibility for educating the pedagogical team. The leader should be able to influence the personality of his subordinates with such a pedagogical culture that, as a result of this influence, the consciousness of each member of the team of pedagogues of this school will be formed, he will have a creative approach to pedagogical work, and actively participate in social life. please The ability of the school director to understand the opinions of his subordinates and representatives of public organizations in the school and quickly draw correct conclusions is important in the proper organization of management work. Educational and economic issues of the school should be discussed in the council, every member of the team of school pedagogues should take the initiative in the implementation of the adopted decisions. It is appropriate to evaluate the work of the leader in school management, not by the time spent on decision-making, but by taking into account the final result of his activity.

The head of the school is responsible for the development of friendly cooperation and mutual assistance in the team of pedagogues. The existence of a good social and psychological atmosphere and situation in the school community depends to a large extent on the relationship between the leader and teachers and educators. It is possible to create a normal pedagogical work situation and correct mutual relations in the team only if there is strong discipline. Strong pedagogical discipline is achieved through the demandingness of the school head, the development of criticism and self-criticism, as well as transparency.

There are many school leaders in our republic who correctly understand the essence of this issue in the school management system, apply the right style of leadership to the educational work of the school, and achieve good results in this regard.

When the leader makes a superficial assessment of the pedagogical work of a teacher or educator, a person's interest in work decreases. Therefore, it is of great importance for the head of the school to record every achievement of the teacher or educator in the field of education, initiative and dexterity that he has shown or is showing. Every school leader should never forget this part of working with employees. Because one of the important conditions for further improvement of the educational work of the school is to correctly assess the work of teaching staff and encourage them.

Elements of management culture include rules of conduct (law and ethics) determined by relevant criteria. Legal criteria are reflected in the jurisprudence

on public education and state legal and regulatory acts, the legal basis of public education, and the Charter of secondary general education schools. General requirements for management personnel are stated in them. Ethics (the science of morality) develops moral standards and rules of everyday conduct. Full compliance with the criteria of ethics in the management of school work is of great importance, because these criteria determine the criteria of law and, together with it, determine the way of behavior of the leader.

School leaders must fully follow these criteria. They rely on ethical criteria such as humanism, kindness, and mutual assistance in their leadership work. At the same time, the social status of the head of the school determines his unique ethics. For example, the head of the school should never give false information (fake) to the higher levels, violate the statistical reporting criteria. In the management culture, it is of particular importance to go beyond the word. Whether you made a promise or an event, fulfill it within the specified time frame. One of the important conditions of the management culture is to treat subordinates fairly and equally, to correctly evaluate their educational work, to praise and encourage them for their success.

IV. The culture of management is to organize management work on the basis of a plan designed on a scientific basis, with a clear goal in mind, to ensure unity of words and practical work, to pay attention to the needs of the school team, students and parents. to be in a relationship with attention and interest, not to touch any of them on the ego, not to engage in showmanship, to introduce a high level of discipline in relation to work, to maintain a high level of pedagogical culture in the process of management, to the leader personally and personally it consists of being demanding to subordinates, not putting one's personal interest above the interest of the state and the community, and so on.

It should be emphasized that the interaction between school leaders and their subordinates - teachers, educators and technical staff of the school is based on a high level of awareness of their own values, ruthlessness towards the violation of society's interests, public and o "Friendly mutual help, humane relations and mutual respect between people, friends, comrades and brothers to each other, honesty and truthfulness in social and private life, moral purity, modesty and modesty, against injustice , includes moral principles such as being intolerant of greed, dishonesty, and greed.

The culture of holding public events among the team of school pedagogues - political, scientific-methodical conferences, methodical councils, seminars, pedagogical readings, meetings, etc. in the framework of the school is also of

great pedagogical importance. The peculiarity of such events is that thanks to these events, it is possible to exchange full and comprehensive information and experience on the discussed issues in a relatively short time. In addition, these activities are considered one of the most effective forms of ideological and educational work in the activity of the pedagogical team. Undoubtedly, such activities have a positive effect on the further improvement of educational work at the school.

Improving management culture means paying more attention to all its areas. This gives an opportunity to increase the efficiency of management, to establish the work of the management apparatus (the work of the school administration) clearly and carefully, and to further strengthen the work discipline of the team of pedagogues. That is why it is necessary to properly organize the leadership style and culture in the school work management system and regularly improve it.

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